

Space object optical tracking system of the UL Academic Centre and its sustainable development

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the framework of the project No 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007 "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" of the second round of the Consolidation and Governance Change Implementation Grants within Investment 5.2.1.1.i "Research, Development and Consolidation Grants" under Reform 5.2.1.r "Higher Education and Science Excellence and Governance Reform" of Reform and Investment Strand 5.2 of the Latvian Recovery and Resilience Mechanism Plan "Ensuring Change in the Governance Model of Higher Education Institutions", postdoctoral research grant project No LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0004: "Space object optical tracking system of the UL Academic Centre and its sustainable development" (project manager: Dr.sc.ing. Diana Haritonova, 1st September 2024 – 31st August 2025, 61 380.00 EUR).

The project's objective is to evaluate effectiveness of the optical tracking system (OTS) of GGI (Institute of Geodesy and Geoinformatics) to perform regular positional astrometric observations of faint near-Earth objects (NEO) and observe space debris. The project will facilitate sustainable development of the OTS for purposes of Space Situational Awareness (SSA) Programme, bring new knowledge and skills to the post-doctoral researcher and students, leading to improvement of the study environment of the University of Latvia. SSA Programme was promoted to become one of the flagship programmes of the European Union. The growing quantity of space debris poses a serious hazard to functioning satellites. On the other hand, near-Earth objects such as asteroids can pose a serious threat to infrastructure and life on the ground. The conducting of such observations is critical.

The main scientific findings will be submitted for publication in international peer-reviewed journal or conference proceeding, which is indexed in the Web of Science Core Collection or SCOPUS databases. Two project proposals will be prepared in a local or international call for research and development projects, which is necessary for the further funding of this scientific research direction at the University of Latvia. Participation in international conferences (at least 2 abstracts) is planned. This research project will contribute to the Smart Specialisation Strategy (RIS3) area “Smart materials, technology and engineering systems”.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Internal and External
Consolidation of the University
of Latvia
(5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Diana Haritonova (0000-0002-4255-9000)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Space object optical tracking system of the UL Academic Centre and its sustainable development](#)

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Researchers:

Diana Haritonova (0000-0002-4255-9000)

Organizations:

University of Latvia

Contact: Haritonova Diana (diana.haritonova@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia
(5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Project: Space object optical tracking system of the UL Academic Centre and its sustainable development

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Positional astrometric observations of NEO and various satellites

Positional astrometric observations by the OTS will be carried out. Continuous monitoring of suitable days and planning of observations is necessary. During each observation night it is planned to perform several sessions for available NEO and satellites. For the purposes of object identification, a locally stored subset of the Gaia star catalogue (data Release

DR3) will be used, consisting of astrometry and star magnitude data for Gaia stars up to magnitude 21.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The main purpose for the data collection is to evaluate effectiveness of the optical tracking system (OTS) of GGI to perform regular positional astrometric observations of faint near-Earth objects (NEO) and observe space debris. Observation of NEO using list of objects needing confirmation is planned with accordance to information provided by the IAU Minor Planet centre. If such objects are not available for observation at the location of OTS, it is planned to use a list of known NEO, provided by NASA's JPL Horizons on-line ephemeris system. Observation of various satellites is planned using available ephemerides: Consolidated Prediction Format (CPF) files, provided by NASA's Crustal Dynamics Data Information System.

Deliverables: data sets of raw and processed CCD frames, observation session protocols.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- Others

BMP, FITS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

A subset of the Gaia star catalogue (data Release DR3). A list of known NEO, provided by NASA's JPL Horizons on-line ephemeris system. Available ephemerides of satellites, provided by NASA's Crustal Dynamics Data Information System.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Target groups are GGI and other scientific institutions representing space research community and performing activities in the relevant branch as well as scientists, technicians, students employed there.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will be made available on request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-08-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Diana Haritonova (0000-0002-4255-9000)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Astrometric observation results of NEO and various satellites

The target application area for the optical tracking system of GGI is ground (in-situ) support of space missions, requiring accurate astrometric position determination of satellites, space debris (SST segment), and small Solar system objects (NEO segment). The main goal is to evaluate effectiveness of the OTS to conduct positional astrometric observations of faint near-Earth objects and various satellites, in particular estimate effectiveness of the system for low-Earth orbit (LEO) satellite observation. Observation results and data processing techniques will be summarized.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The main purpose is to provide information on the effectiveness of the OTS to conduct astrometric observations of faint near-Earth objects and observe space debris.

Deliverables: tables of asteroid parameters and satellite characteristics (visual magnitudes, speed, rotational period), conclusions.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF

- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, I have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The scientific findings of this research project will be useful for all members of the international space research community, including scientists of the Republic of Latvia.

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No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

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2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-10-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

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